

Flexible Arrangement as a Non-Monetary Rewards and Employee Performance in Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital, Kenya

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Abstract: Monetary and non-monetary rewards are important in any given organization, non-monetary rewards are more effective determinants of employee satisfaction. The purpose of the study was examine the effect of flexible schedules on employee performance at the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital. The study adopted a descriptive research approach which helped in using quantitative techniques to establish the relationship between the variables. The target population of the study was drawn from the top employees at Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital. The population comprised of 150 top employees. The sample for the research was determined using the Yamane formula. The sample size of 120 respondents was apportioned to the top employees. The main data collection instrument for this research was a structured research questionnaire. The collected study data was analyzed using a mix of descriptive and inferential statistics. The results were presented using figures and tables in line with the objectives of the study. Findings showed that there was a strong relationship between the independent and employee performance at Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital. The study recommends that the management of the hospital the hospital should also create flexi-time work arrangements which help employees in managing their work-life balance and that the hospital has created a part-time working schedule for our employees to ensure their optimal work output.

Keywords: non-monetary rewards, flexible arrangement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding incentives is the first step towards recognising how incentives affect employee performance. The success of an organization is highly dependent on the motivation of employees (Lee & Raschke, 2016). Employee happiness and company success depends on both monetary and non-monetary incentives, but achieving a good balance between the two may be challenging. Both alternatives are popular with both employers and employees and can theoretically influence the hiring and retention of employees (Chaudhary & Ghosh, 2017). Globally, populations are getting younger and more exposed to certain standards, and in the case of employees, Kurdi, Alshurideh and Alnaser (2020) assert that high performance and loyalty can be determined by certain reward systems. Similar reports were made in the study by Osborne and Hammoud (2017), determining that in today's turbulent and chaotic environment, increasing employee competence through effective engagement can maximize employees' use of their talents and reach their full potential. Further, the study by Al Aina and Atan (2020) asserts that increased organizational productivity and performance is reliant on its ability to attract, retain and develop talented employees.

Paul and Vincent (2018) opined that motivated employees are more likely to be dedicated to meeting firm goals and are easier to retain. Managers are increasingly being challenged to explore rewards systems that can effectively motivate employees towards improved performance (Hoole & Hotz, 2016). Krstic (2018), on the other hand argues that motivating employees to work towards achieving personal goals is key to improved workplace productivity. However, according to Altındağ (2015), managers have been struggling to balance between meeting the personal needs of employees and mandates of the organization. The organisational productivity depends on the efforts of the satisfied employees. Tumi, Hasan and Khalid (2022) study affirms that implementing an effective compensation system, job enrichment, appropriate training are among the main challenges facing organizations that attempt to motivate employees. The researchers affirmed that telecommunication firms should formulate appropriate compensation systems composed of monetary and non-monetary rewards, provide job training to enhance knowledge and skills, as well as offer job enrichment and enlargement opportunities to expand employees' motivation as this would improve organizational success. In the construction industry, Holston-Okae and Mushi (2018) states that these challenges are exacerbated by healthcare workers working environment which is complex, resource-intensive and involves delicate collaborative partnerships. Further, Al Karim (2019) affirms that hospital workers in Malaysia have different competencies, from highly trained and highly skilled technical and clinical staff members to unskilled workers. For managers to realize sustained performances in such setups, they have to be able to manage and motivate a wide array of employees (Krstic, 2018). Employee performance is defined as how best an employee performs their duties and behaves at the workplace (Pradhan & Jena, 2016). Employee performance is critical to any organization to realize organizational sustainability and growth (Sungmala & Verawat, 2021). Various studies have sought after the factors that influence employee performance, with multiple associating higher employee motivation with positive employee performance outcomes (Rozi & Sunarsi, 2020; Pang & Lu, 2018; Breaugh, Ritz, & Alfes, 2018). These studies were not based on healthcare sector firms.

Baljoon, Banjar and Banakhar (2018) studied nurses' motivation factors in a study which identified the firm's empowerment practices, pay and financial benefits, work engagement, supervision, career development, contingent rewards, workplace relationships, communication and the nature of work as the organizational factors that affect nurses' motivation to meet workplace demands. Gunawan, Aunguroch and Fisher (2019) study concluded that healthcare firms have to incorporate competence-based reward systems as they significantly improve nurses' performance. Abraham Maslow's (1943) Theory of Human Motivation is the most popular reference explaining the determinants of motivation, human needs and individual behavior (Jerome, 2013). According to Maslow (1943), human behavior is motivated by specific needs. Maslow (1943) identifies physiological, safety, love and belonging, esteem, and self-actualization needs as the core needs that dictate human behavior. In similar fashion, (De Vito, Brown, Bannister, Cianci, & Mujtaba, 2018) asserts that employees will not perform optimally if certain needs are not met, and will exhibit a higher degree of motivation if certain needs are met. Maslow (1943) affirms that people have a pyramided hierarchy of needs, with some being essential/common, and others more individualistic. This theory asserts that satisfaction varies from one individual to another. Healthcare sector firms face the challenge of attracting, satisfying, retaining and developing key positions, and this has led to unsatisfactory employee performance. According to the study by Nzyoka and Orwa (2016) a total compensation system is essential for positive employee performance in the insurance industry.

According to Mokhniuk and Yushchyshyna (2018), although both monetary and non-monetary rewards are important in any given organization, non-monetary rewards are more effective determinants of employee satisfaction. Jaleta, Kero and Kumera (2019) states that recent literature has been redirected towards the relationship between non-financial incentives and employee performance, and Maslow's Theory has provided core theoretical perspective. Jaleta et al (2019) determined that aside from financial compensation, empowerment, recognition and work conditions have a significant impact on Health center employees' performance. Kitsios and Kamariotou (2021) assert that health workers who are highly motivated and satisfied with their jobs contribute to success of the health care industry. Brooks (2015) confirms that determining the best employee reward system has been a challenge for many Bosnian hospitals and this has negatively impacted the nurses' motivation, productivity and overall organizational efficiency. Reward systems have been used over time by human resource management to stimulate employee performance (Ginbar, 2020). Studies on the effects of reward systems on employee performance have revealed that employee performance is highly affected by reward systems used in any given organization (Noorazem et al., 2021). These findings are supported in the study by Waithira (2018), who reported that the reward system used by an organization determines the degree of employee motivation and performance outcomes.

Turnea and Prodan (2020) identified financial and non-financial 4 rewards in a study which determined that reward system variables such as compensation, benefits, work-life balance, career opportunities and development, and performance and recognition determine an organization's attractiveness to prospective employees, and their intentions to remain contracted in the long-term. Monetary rewards are among the most common parts of the reward system and although they are not necessarily the most essential parts of the system, they have a high impact on employee motivation (Siddiqui, 2019). Monetary rewards can be based on performance-based salary increases, short-term incentives or long-term incentives. Non-monetary reward refers to noncash benefits provided to the employee by an employer (Fisher, 2016). Non-monetary reward, on the other hand include flexible working hours, planned career breaks, sabbatical/study leave, access to training opportunities, holidays, recreational facilities, recognition, flexible schedules and occupational health counselling (Khan et al., 2016).

Agbenyegah (2019) notes that an effective reward system should contain both financial and non-financial elements, despite non-monetary rewards having a more significant effect on employee commitment. Non-monetary rewards are those firm specific factors that determine firm performance and employee recognition is one of the key determinants of high employee retention and low turnover intentions (Apuko, 2021). Over the recent past due to economic decline there is an increase adaptation and use of non-monetary rewards in organizations to ensure that the employees stay motivated and yield better results (OECD, 2020). Research on the effects of team-based goals and non-monetary incentives on front-line health worker performance and maternal health behaviours in India, reveals team-based goals and non-monetary incentives improves team-based performance (Carmichael et al., 2019). Okeke and Ikechukwu (2019) argues that although organizations have to regularly reward their employees, in sub-Saharan Africa, lack of effective reward systems has resulted in a sharp reduction in the number of workers and a high rate of employee turnover. Lema (2020) investigated the effects of nonmonetary factors on job performance in public institutions looking at Arusha City Council, Tanzania and determined that non-monetary rewards such as recognition, job security, and training improve job performance. Another study looking at non-monetary incentives on employee performance at banks in Ghana, revealed that there exists a linear relationship between non-monetary incentives and employee performance (Adom et al., 2020). Waithira (2018) in her study on effects of rewards strategies on employee performance in Kenya, a case of farm concern international showed non-monetary rewards being employed in the firm were favourably received and were spurring employee performance. However, the researcher asserts that to achieve the desired employee performance, the reward system should be aligned to organizational strategies, goals, and values.

The Kenya Health Policy 2014 - 2030, (2014), shows the health sector is committed to meeting public services in a sustainable means under government stewardship to ensure that the country reaches the highest possible standards of health. The major challenges in providing health care services in Kenya includes terms of service, cost of services, staffing of health personnel (Davis, Menser, Juarez, Tomaszewski, & Kash, 2018). These challenges have impacted healthcare center's ability to attract and retain their staff due to the terms and conditions of services, especially doctors (Kinyili, 2018). Tengah and Otieno (2019) concede that Kenya has a high rate of public health practitioner turnover which has had a negative impact on the quality of healthcare afforded to patients. Poor health worker retention results to disadvantaged and poorly serviced populations (Kimathi, 2017). As a measure against attrition, human resources main function is to attract and retain quality employees (Castro Lopes et al., 2017). Various strategies have been identified as essential to enhancing staff retention in the healthcare sector. Golicha and Moguche (2022) identify talent management practices as essential drivers of employee retention in referral hospitals in Kenya. Yeswa and Ombui (2019) study identified improved quality of training, career development and a suitable work environment as effective strategies for enhancing employee retention.

Flexible working refers to a state whereby employees have a high degree of control over when or where they work (Dizaho, Salleh, & Abdullah, 2017). De Stefano (2015) also includes breaks in career, job sharing and part-time and term-time as components of flexi-work arrangements. According to Deb (2020), flexible work schedules enable employees to work outside of normal routines and can be narrowed to flexibility in scheduling (flexi-time), flexibility in location (teleworking), and flexibility in length of the work (part-time). Deb (2020) reports that flexible work arrangements vary significantly with their embrace being attributed to emerging technologies. Flexible working practices have been documented to positively contribute to employee motivation hence increased employee productivity and higher organization profitability, especially among younger employees (Kipkoech, 2018; Ochieng & Kamau, 2021). Deloitte (2018) affirm that majority of millennials would appreciate the opportunity to work from home. However, according to Groen, Van Triest, Coers and Wtenweerde

(2018), flexible work arrangements have to be designed appropriately since they can have a negative impact on employee output.

Further, Chung (2020) study showed that flexi-work schedules can have a negative impact on women's career development opportunities in the UK. Training and career development refers to the efforts instituted to increase individual's skills, competencies and status in a well-defined career path (Litano & Major, 2016). According to Fahed-Sreih (2020), intervening to improve the technical skills of employees within a plan for their future enables maximum growth of both the employee and the organization.

Baljoon, Banjar and Banakhar (2018) reports that while male nurses were motivated by training and career development, female healthcare workers were highly motivated by recognition and flexible work arrangements. Patel, Sekhri, Bhimanadham, Imran and Hossain (2019) identified poor working conditions characterized by long work shifts, stressful on-call duties, lack of appreciation, and poor social interactions factors contribute to burnout among physicians. The Global Health Workforce Statistics Database (2022) reports that Sub-Saharan Africa faces a great challenge with regards to poor health indicators and low health worker to population ratios and therefore requires extensive research on rewards towards health worker motivation. This challenge has been attributed to lack of defined career paths, low salaries, inadequate quality training and unsafe working environment among health workers. Consequently, health worker issues are not examined on a comprehensive approach (Oleribe et al., 2019; Jasemi et al., 2017). An examination into the effect of reward systems on motivation and healthcare worker performance is necessary to address some of the challenges affecting the sector (Oyira et al., 2015; Global Health Workforce Alliance, 2008). Motivation of employees results in satisfactory performance as well as job satisfaction, hence excellent job retention rates (Okoth & Oluoch, 2019). Patel, Sekhri, Bhimanadham, Imran and Hossain (2019) affirmed that health workers can be motivated internally through comprehensive professional training, introduction of stress reducing activities and implementation of work-hour limitations recommended by Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education (ACGME).

Rewards are essential in retaining healthy workers in remote environments. Countries such as South Africa, Zambia and Lesotho have employed reward system such as rural allowances to retain health workers in rural environment and has shown good retention rate. Rewards therefore play a significant role in attracting health workers and retaining them (Baljoon, Banjar, & Banakhar, 2018). According to the Kenya Medical Practitioners and Dentists Board (KMPDB), Kenya has registered around 9,000 medical doctors and 1,000 dentists over the past 32 years, but only 75 per cent of these are currently considered "active", having renewed their medical licences within the past five years. Further, Kenya has just 1.03 health workers (doctors, nurses, midwives, and clinical officers) per 1,000 population compared with the WHO recommendation of 2.30 per 1,000 population. This signifies a low rate of retention which can have a negative impact on national healthcare delivery.

Organizational performance can be raised to the highest level by offering non-monetary rewards to the workers/employees (Heyman & Ariely, 2004). Al Aina and Atan (2020) asserts that increased organizational productivity and performance is reliant on its ability to attract, retain and develop talented employees. Paul and Vincent (2018) opined that motivated employees are more likely to be dedicated to meeting firm goals and are easier to retain. The performance of an organization is affected by how the employees are valued and rewarded (Salah, 2016). Poor implementation of proper reward frameworks has a negative impact on employee morale, commitment and motivation resulting in poor organization performance. Over the recent past, emphasis on motivational programs has been outlined in different literature and human resource management studies as tool towards organization success (Stewart & Brown, 2019). According to Murphy (2015), reward systems have varying impacts on employee attitudes towards work.

Tumi, Hasan and Khalid (2022) found that having the correct reward system and targeting it in the right way can generate a positive desire to meet organizational goals and support employee empowerment. Despite establishing and formalizing regular payment schemes, lack of rewards systems in many sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) nations has resulted in a decrease in the number of workers regionally, with a large number of professionals migrating to countries with better compensation systems (Moruri, et al., 2018). Physicians in developing countries are often underpaid and carry more stress due to low physician-to-patient ratio, contributing to high burnout (Khan, et al., 2020). Understanding the factors that influence employee performance, especially in the health sector is key to ensuring effective service delivery. Stewart and Brown (2019) affirm that there is an increase in the volume of explorations into the relationship between both monetary, non-monetary rewards and staff performance. However, the existing research on non-monetary rewards and health worker

performance is limited and there is a need to update existing literature (Scott et al., 2018). In China, Ma, Wang, Yang, Shi and Liu (2019) asserted that realigning rewards systems is key to realizing improved performance in the healthcare sector. In Bangladesh, Hosain (2019) showed how non-financial rewards had emerged as effective sources of competitive advantage that firms use to attract qualified personnel.

Asaari, Desa and Subramaniam (2019) aver that within government trade agencies, salaries, promotion and recognition are the main determinants of workplace motivation. However, according to Kollmann, Stöckmann, Kensbock and Peschl (2020) younger employees are more motivated with greater degrees of independence, recognition and a supportive work environment. Mani and Mishra (2020) concluded that HR practitioners can leverage growth, renewal, enabling, aspirational and transparency levers to enhance employee motivation during the COVID-19 pandemic. In Kenya, most organizations offer monetary rewards such as pay rise, bonuses as opposed to non-monetary rewards such as an opportunity to contribute to key decision, employee independence, and recognition (Muriuki, 2016 ; Ngatia, 2017). Studies done to evaluate the impact of non-monetary studies on employee performance use a few characteristics as a measure of non-monetary rewards that is career development (Lesya Ukrainka et al., 2018). This is attributed limited knowledge on non-monetary rewards and their impact on employee performance (Ngatia, 2017). In addition, these organizations rarely embrace flexible working schedules, and most employees are accustomed to early mornings that interfere with social and family set ups. Therefore, most of this organization are still using traditional rewarding systems and there exists a gap on non-monetary rewards and how they affect employee performance and offer competitive advantage to an organization and how well they can be used to improve employee performance in an organization (Tebetso Tshukudu, 2020). There is a paucity of literature on the combined effect of recognition, career development, employee independence, and flexible schedules as non-monetary rewards on staff performance among health workers (Cross et al., 2019). This study therefore proposed to examine the effect of flexible schedules on employee performance at the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital, Kenya.

2. FLEXIBLE SCHEDULE AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

In Today's world, employee demand out of workstation on social and family and sports grounds as well as other activities is inevitable. A flexible working schedule and occasional afternoon off would be important for the employee to attend to personal roles. Flexible working schedules contribute to employee motivation hence increased employee productivity and higher organization profitability (Ochieng & Kamau, 2021). Austin-Egole, Iheriohanma and Nwokorie (2020) carried out a review into the relationship between flexible working arrangements and organizational performance. The methodology involved library research involving analytical discussion of secondary data. The analysis showed that weekend work, part-time work, annual hours contract, flexi-time and job-sharing were some of the most effective work arrangements that improved employee engagement and commitment. The study called for more research into the effects of employee-driven and employer-driven flexible work arrangements on organizational performance.

Schlak, Aiken, Chittams, Poghosyan and McHugh (2021) sought after how hospitals can leverage the work environment to realize organizational goals and reduce nurse burnout using a large sample of 523 US hospitals. The study used a cross-sectional design and employed multivariate logistic regressions in analysis. The analysis determined that poor scheduling and staffing had contributed to increased nurse burnout in lower ranked hospitals. However, hospitals designated with the Magnet Recognition standard which is an indicator of a good work environment recorded lower burnout which has a direct impact on nurse performance. A good work environment where the nurses were allowed to decide how long to work and when to take job-breaks was determined to attenuate the relationship between nurse burnout and mortality, failure to rescue, and length of stay. This study was based on the more developed US market while the current study bases its findings on a developing economy which has not yet fully integrated non-monetary rewards.

Hwang (2019) explored the effects of organizational culture on job satisfaction, job stress and nurses' happiness in a study which involved seventeen hospitals in South Korea with greater than 100 beds. The study applied a multiple regression analysis to examine the factors that determine the happiness of the nurses. Conclusions were that the nurses were unhappy due to high work load, a result-oriented culture and minimum freedom. Letting the nurses play a part in scheduling, and selection of benefits would increase nurses' happiness and increase patient engagement. This study analysed job performance as opposed to job satisfaction. Davidescu, Apostu, Paul and Casuneanu (2020) investigated the relationship between work flexibility, job satisfaction and performance among employees in Romania. Data was gathered through a national representative survey using multiple correspondence analysis. The impact of individual and employee flexibility on overall job satisfaction was quantified using binary logistic regression models. Logistic regression analysis showed that

functional flexibility, working time, and workspace flexibility have a positive effect on employee's level of job satisfaction and performance. This study was based on all industries while the current examined employee performance in the health sector. Dousin, Collins and Kler (2019) examined the impact of work-life balance practices on the performance of doctors and nurses in East Malaysia. Specific objectives were on the effect of flexible working hours and supportive supervision on job satisfaction and job performance. The research employed a quantitative methodology and used a survey questionnaire in data collection. Pearson correlation analysis determined that flexible working hours and supportive supervision both have a positive and significant impact on job performance. The research concluded that having an effective set of Work Life Balance (WLB) practices will improve employees' job satisfaction which eventually increases their job performance and productivity. This study was done in East Malaysia while the current study analysed the same within the Kenyan sector. Further, the current study focused on one firms' non-monetary rewards.

White and Miniam (2020) investigated the relationship between flexible working arrangements, work-life balance, and performance of working women in America. The researchers carried out an extensive literature review towards this end noting that flexibility is different to employers and workers and significantly different between male and female employers. The analysis determined that companies incentivize employees through flexible schedules such as flexible hours, additional half days, remote work, and other options as these factors were associated with increased employee performance and productivity. The study also recommended companies provide flexibility based on tenure rather than performance as this would inspire a higher level of organizational commitment. This study focused on nonmonetary rewards for women while the current study analysed the effect of non-monetary rewards on the performance of both genders. Dousin, Collins and Kler (2022) investigated work-life balances implemented in hospitals in Malaysia to determine their effect on female doctors and nurses experience. The study adopted a qualitative study and collected data from 26 participants using in-depth, semi-structured interviews. Analysis involved a systematic multi-step data analytical procedure which determined that while collegiality at work facilitates work-life balance, staff shortages in the healthcare sector were impeding health institution's ability to effectively institute work-life balance practices such as job-sharing and flexible work schedules. The result was higher pressure for women doctors to balance between personal and professional goals and this conflict impacted their goal realization. This study also investigated work-life balance practices specific to women while the current involved all employees.

Khan, et al., (2020) examined the work life balance practices adopted by private tertiary care hospitals in Karachi in a cross-sectional study. The study sought after the relationship between job satisfaction, emotional wellbeing and personal life. Correlational analysis determined that the medical residents felt that there was a high degree of friction between job demands and their private life. This led to burn-out and dissatisfaction with work related roles. The study recommended reduced work hours, greater mentorship and support from respective departments, clarity of assignment and learning outlines, and increased mentorship and growth opportunities to ensure the residents are comfortable and more willing to meet work roles. This study looked at the effect of non-monetary rewards on performance of nurses in private tertiary care hospitals while the current expounded the findings to a public referral hospital.

Fuentes (2019) sought after the effect of implementing a self-scheduling model on nurses' performance outcomes. The study implemented the model in a medical-surgical unit using quality improvement steps of the Deming Plan-Do-Check-Act approach. The study carried out surveys and interviews across a 90-day period and determined that empowering nurses through a self-scheduling model resulted in positive performance outcomes and reduced burnout and turnover intentions. This study was specific to the influence of self-scheduling models on nurses' performance while the current examined how application of multiple non-financial rewards impact employee performance. Abid and Barech (2017) evaluated the impact of flexible working hours on the employees of telecommunication/call centers performance. The study adopted a descriptive research design and collected data from telecommunication/call center employees. Convenient sampling was utilized. Results from this study showed that flexible work hours have a high impact on productivity: on employee performance and improves the work life balance.

In a similar study, Kipkoech (2018) examined the effect of flexi-work on employee performance in Kericho county referral hospital using a descriptive research design. The study's population consisted of top management, doctors, clinical officers, nurses and subordinates. Stratified sampling was used. Data was collected using open and closed ended questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The results from this study indicate that flexible working schedules are significant to employee performance. These two studies were specific to the influence of flexible working patterns while the current study

addressed how multiple reward systems impact employee performance outcomes. Okemwa (2016) sought after the relationship between flexible working arrangements and commitment of nurses in public hospitals in Kenya. The study adopted cross sectional survey design and targeted 1217 nurses from level 4 and 5 public hospitals. The researcher utilized simple random sampling to select participating counties and proportionate random sampling to select participating hospitals. Linear regression analysis was applied to the data collected using questionnaires, revealing that flexible work arrangements such as flexi-time, compressed work schedule, shift schedule and job sharing all have a positive relationship with nurses' level of commitment. This study failed to investigate how other reward systems influence employee commitment and its relationship with performance outcomes.

Employee performance is achieving and accomplishing specific and well-determined tasks in the organization, these tasks will be measured with well-planned and predefined goals, objectives (Safitri & Lathifah, 2019). Armstrong (2020), stated that employee performance management is the continuous process of improving performance by setting individual and team goals that are aligned to the strategic goals of the organization, planning performance to achieve the goals, reviewing and assessing progress, and developing the knowledge, skills, and abilities of people (Armstrong, 2020). Some of the main performance measurements are productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, quality and profitability (Aidan, 2013; Armstrong, 2020). Employee performance demonstrated the improvement in production by perfect use of new technology with the help of highly aggravated employees (Al-Omari et al., Citation 2020). Manger used to set high standards for individual in order to measure the performance of employees for the betterment of organization (Buchanan. & Badham, 2020).

Employee performance signifies an individual's work achievement after exerting the required effort on the job, which is associated with getting meaningful work, engaging profile, and compassionate colleagues/employers (Hellriegel, Jackson, & Slocum, 1999; Karakas, 2010). Improving performance has become one of the most important goals for several organizations because higher levels of productivity lead to favorable economic growth, large profitability, and better social progress (Hanaysha, 2016; Sharma & Sharma, 2014). In fact, (Hill et al., 2014) noted that higher performance tends to maximize organizational competitive advantage through cost reductions and improvement in high-quality output (Hanaysha, 2016). Employee Performance is fundamental component that facilitates organizational growth and sustainability, specifically being affected by the reward system employed in an organization (Ngulube, 2003). Over the last few decades the world business environment has undergone a radical transformation. The world has become smaller, not physically, but in terms of communications, competition and economics. This has radically changed the way successful organizations do business and how they look at their employees. This transformation has impacted the private sector significantly and is impacting the public sector as well, both in direct and indirect ways. Global organizations are becoming more responsive to their customers, reducing costs, and improving quality (Erbasi, 2012). Today's customer demands value in both products as well as services. Even more significantly, customers do not have to tolerate sub-par performance because they can readily turn to alternative sources that offer faster, cheaper, better and more innovative products and services.

The organizations that are succeeding in this global environment are those that have recognized that their people are the greatest factor in their success. New organizations that are evolving place a greater value on employees than organizations had in the past, and they achieve more by creating a process for employees to share in the results that they help achieve. Thus, today's successful organizations match their employee reward systems to their strategies, goals and values (Ballentine, 2007).

3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The study targeted 193 (153 rocketreach) top employees. The study adopted random sampling in the selection of the research participants. The Yamane formula given below was used to determine the sample size. From the Yamane formula, the sample size for the research was 150 respondents who was drawn from the hospital employees. Data collection instrument was questionnaire and other information relevant to the study. A structured questionnaire was administered to the respondents. The research instrument was pretested at KMTC Nakuru so as not to interfere with the study sample. A pilot group of ten (10) percent of respondents will be targeted which is 15 respondents. The findings of the pilot study was used to improve the data collection instruments. Piloting was done for testing the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. The data was reduced, organized, coded, edited, classified using a table and analyzed to bring out the meaning under each of the factors. Data was collected, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was then be coded, entered and analyzed descriptively

using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SSPS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis was adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSION

The study sought to examine the effect of flexible schedules on employee performance at the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital. The findings are presented in a five point Likerts scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total. From table 4.1 below, the respondents were asked whether the organisation provides employees with paid parental leave to foster their work productivity and allows employees to obtain compassionate leave and paid time-off as part of the human resource policy. The distribution of findings showed that 38.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 30.0 percent of them agreed, 28.0 percent of the respondents were neutral, 3.0 percent disagreed while 1.0 percent of them strongly disagreed. These findings implied that the organisation provides employees with paid parental leave to foster their work productivity and allows employees to obtain compassionate leave and paid time-off as part of the human resource policy.

The respondents were also asked whether the organisation provides employees with adequate time for leisure activities and personal development. The distribution of the responses indicated that 30.3 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 52.5 percent of them agreed, 15.2 percent of them were neutral, 1.0 percent of them disagreed while 1.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that the organisation provides employees with adequate time for leisure activities and personal development.

The respondents were also asked whether the organisation ensures there is strict adherence to work rotation schedules to ensure employees are not overburdened. The distribution of the responses indicated that 28.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 54.0 percent of them agreed, 15.0 percent of them were neutral, 2.0 percent of them disagreed while 1.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied the organisation ensures there is strict adherence to work rotation schedules to ensure employees are not overburdened. The respondents were further asked whether the organisation provides employees with regular counselling and guidance programmes to improve their mental well-being. The distribution of the responses indicated that 27.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 52.0 percent of them agreed, 16.0 percent of them were neutral while 3.0 percent and 2.0 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that the organisation provides employees with regular counselling and guidance programmes to improve their mental well-being.

Further, the respondents were asked whether the organisation has created flexi-time work arrangements which help employees in managing their work-life balance. The distribution of the responses indicated that 35.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 40.0 percent of them agreed, 24.0 percent of them were neutral, 1.0 percent of them disagreed while 0.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that the organisation has created flexi-time work arrangements which help employees in managing their work-life balance. Finally, the respondents were asked whether the organisation has created a part-time working schedule for our employees to ensure their optimal work output. The distribution of the responses indicated that 23.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 27.0 percent of them agreed, 30.0 percent of them were neutral, 12.0 percent of them disagreed while 18.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that the organisation has created a part-time working schedule for our employees to ensure their optimal work output.

Table 4.1: Effect of Flexible Schedules on Employee Performance at the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital

Statements		SA	A	N	D	SD
The organisation provides employees with paid parental leave to foster their work productivity and allows employees to obtain compassionate leave and paid time-off as part of the human resource policy.	%	38.0	30.0	28.0	3.0	1.0
The organisation provides employees with adequate time for leisure activities and personal development	%	30.3	52.5	15.2	1.0	1.0

The organisation ensures there is strict adherence to work rotation schedules to ensure employees are not overburdened	%	28.0	54.0	15.0	2.0	1.0
The organisation provides employees with regular counselling and guidance programmes to improve their mental well-being	%	27.0	52.0	16.0	3.0	2.0
The organisation has created flexi-time work arrangements which help employees in managing their work-life balance	%	35.0	40.0	24.0	1.0	0.0
The organisation has created a part-time working schedule for our employees to ensure their optimal work output	%	23.0	27.0	30.0	12.0	18.0

4.1 Effect of Employee Performance at the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital

Lastly, the study sought to examine the effect of employee performance at the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital. The findings are presented in a five point Likerts scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total.

From table 4.2 below, the respondents were asked whether there is efficient execution of all the duties assigned by supervisors to meet the organizational set goals. The distribution of findings showed that 44.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 41.0 percent of them agreed, 13.0 percent of the respondents were neutral while 2.0 percent disagreed. None of the respondents strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that there is efficient execution of all the duties assigned by supervisors to meet the organizational set goals.

The respondents were also asked whether the required quality standards are effectively observed in the institution. The distribution of the responses indicated that 24.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 53.0 percent of them agreed and 19.0 percent of them were neutral while 3.0 percent of them disagreed. 1.0 percent of the respondents strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that the required quality standards are effectively observed in the institution. The respondents were also asked whether multiple task assigned by superiors are handled to enhance the quantity of work completed under minimal time. The distribution of the responses indicated that 28.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 47.0 percent of them agreed, 24.0 percent of them were neutral while 0.0 and 1.0 percent of them disagreed and strongly disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that multiple task assigned by superiors are handled to enhance the quantity of work completed under minimal time.

The respondents were further asked whether there is collaboration among co-workers to support better attainment of the organization goals and objectives. The distribution of the responses indicated that 39.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 38.0 percent of them agreed while 21.0 percent of them were neutral. 2.0 percent of the respondents disagreed while none strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that there is collaboration among co-workers to support better attainment of the organization goals and objectives. The respondents were further asked whether the set job duties and responsibilities can be done to maximize productivity with proper channels of communication. The distribution of the responses indicated that 31.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 49.0 percent of them agreed while 17.0 percent of them were neutral. 2.0 percent of the respondents disagreed and 1.0 percent strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that the set job duties and responsibilities can be done to maximize productivity with proper channels of communication.

Table 4.2: Effect of Employee Performance at the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital

Statements		SA	A	N	D	SD
There is efficient execution of all the duties assigned by supervisors to meet the organizational set goals	%	44.0	41.0	13.0	2.0	0

The required quality standards are effectively observed in the institution	%	24.0	53.0	19.0	3.0	1.0
Multiple task assigned by superiors are handled to enhance the quantity of work completed under minimal time	%	28.0	47.0	24.0	0.0	1.0
There is collaboration among co-workers to support better attainment of the organization goals and objectives	%	39.0	38.0	21.0	2.0	0
The set job duties and responsibilities can be done to maximize productivity with proper channels of communication	%	31	49.0	17.0	2.0	1.00

4.2 Inferential Statistics

4.2.1 Pearson Correlation

The study sought to establish the strength of the relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study. Pearson correlation coefficient was computed at 95 percent confidence interval (error margin of 0.05). Table 4.3 illustrates the findings of the study.

Table 4.3: Correlation matrix

		Flexible schedule	Employee performance
Flexible schedules	Pearson Correlation	1	.174
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.085
	N	120	120
Employee performance	Pearson Correlation	.174	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.085	
	N	120	120

As shown on Table 4.3 above, the p-value for flexible schedule was found to be 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, ($p < 0.05$). The result indicated that Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.376, which represented a strong, positive relationship between flexible schedule and employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital.

4.2.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regressions were computed at 95 percent confidence interval (0.05 margin error) to show the multiple linear relationship between the independent and dependent variable of the study.

4.2.2.1 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 4.4 shows that the coefficient of correlation (R) is positive 0.231. This means that there is a positive correlation between effect of non-monetary rewards and employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital. The coefficient of determination (R Square) indicates that 53.0% of employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital is influenced by the non-monetary rewards. The adjusted R^2 however, indicates that 13.0% of employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital is influenced by the effect of non-monetary rewards leaving 87.0% to be influenced by other factors that were not captured in this study.

Table 4.4 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.231 ^a	.053	.013	.2474210

a. Predictors: (Constant), Flexible Schedules

4.2.2.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 4.5 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The p-value is 0.000 which is < 0.05 indicates that the model is statistically significant in predicting how non-monetary reward affects employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital. The results also indicate that the independent variables are predictors of the dependent variable.

Table 4.5 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.245	1	1.302	1.351	.227 ^b
	Residual	91.364	119	.973		
	Total	96.609	120			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital

b. Predictors: (Constant), Flexible Schedules

4.2.2.3 Regression Coefficients

From the Coefficients table (Table 4.6) the regression model can be derived as follows:

$$Y = 0.008 + 0.144 X_3$$

The results in table 4.6 indicate that all the independent variables have a significant positive effect on employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital. The influential variable is flexible schedules with a coefficient of 0.144 (p-value = 0.194). According to this model when the independent variable values are zero, employee performance in employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital will have a score of 0.008.

Table 4.6 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	.008	.100		.078	.938
	Flexible schedules	.144	.110	.143	1.307	.194

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital

4.2.3 Hypotheses Testing

H₀₃: Flexible schedule does not have a significant effect on employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital.

From Table 4.6 above, flexible schedule ($\beta = 0.144$) was found to be positively related employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 1.307 and the p-value 0.194. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that flexible schedules affects employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study sought to examine the effect of flexible schedules on employee performance at the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital. The findings implied that the hospital provides employees with paid parental leave to foster their work productivity and allows employees to obtain compassionate leave and paid time-off as part of the human resource policy. These findings implied that the hospital provides employees with adequate time for leisure activities and personal development. The findings also revealed that the hospital ensures there is strict adherence to work rotation schedules to ensure employees are not overburdened and that the hospital provides employees with regular counselling and guidance programmes to improve their mental well-being. Further, the findings implied that the hospital has created flexi-time work arrangements which help employees in managing their work-life balance and that the hospital has created a part-time working schedule for employees to ensure their optimal work output. In conclusion basing on the findings, Flexible schedules ($\beta = 0.144$) was found to be positively related employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 1.307 and the p-value 0.194. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that flexible schedules affects employee performance in Moi referral and teaching hospital. The study recommended that the hospital should provide employees with paid parental leave to foster their work productivity and allows employees to obtain compassionate leave and paid time-off as part of the human resource policy. The hospital should create flexi-time work arrangements which help employees in managing their work-life balance and that the hospital has created a part-time working schedule for our employees to ensure their optimal work output.

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